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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING
DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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ERA POLICY BRIEF

CALL: H2020-IBA-SWAFS-SUPPORT-2-2020

TOPIC: SUPPORT FOR THE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION DIMENSION OF EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES (PART II)

PROJECT: ENLIGHT Research and Innovation agenda with and for SociEty (ENLIGHT RISE)

<https://enlight-eu.org/>

SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

In this policy brief, the European Universities pilot alliances report on the progress made through cooperation in selected R&I areas and provide a first set of recommendations to the European Commission for further policy development.

Policy background:

In order to strengthen strategic partnerships across the EU amongst higher education institutions, the European Commission targets the emergence of “European Universities” by 2024 by funding alliances from across Europe. The ambitious mandate aims to trigger systemic, structural and sustainable institutionalized cooperation between higher education institutions. As a complement to the Erasmus+ action geared towards supporting higher education cooperation models, Horizon 2020 support is dedicated to contributing to the research and innovation dimension of the alliances between European universities, in line with their shared, integrated, long-term joint strategy and in synergy with their education dimension.

This initiative is one of the flagships of the European strategy for universities that aims at supporting and enabling universities to adapt to changing conditions, to thrive and to take a leading role in the recovery of Europe, and in making our society greener, more inclusive and more digital. The adoption of this strategy was accompanied by a Commission proposal for a Council recommendation on building bridges for effective European higher education cooperation.

In parallel, the European Research Area Policy Agenda sets out 20 voluntary actions for the period 2022-2024, including several of which are relevant for universities. The feedback from the alliances will help co-shape the design and implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda 2022 – 2024, such as ERA actions 1 (sharing of data), 3 (reform of research management), 4 (strengthening careers), 5 (gender equality), 7 (knowledge valorisation), 8 (research infrastructures), 13 (empowering universities), 14 (engaging citizens), 15 (role in R&I ecosystem), 17 (research management capacity).

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS (MAX 1.5P)

1. Please describe the **challenges** your Alliance encountered regarding cooperation between universities in the field of R&I in relation to the institutional change areas (transformation modules) foreseen.

Challenges encountered by the alliance

The ENLIGHT Alliance has encountered several challenges regarding cross-university cooperation in the field of R&I over the course of the RISE project. While these difficulties have varied in scope and intensity since the beginning of RISE, recurring challenges with regards to timeline, funding, and cooperation have remained relevant obstacles that the alliance has faced.

As described in the first Policy Brief, one of the main difficulties faced by the ENLIGHT alliance has been the different timelines and funding of its two projects: “ENLIGHT RISE”, and the educational component supported by Erasmus+ for the period of 2023 to 2027 (referred to herein as “ENLIGHT 2.0”). Despite their different goals, there are overlapping topics that require coordination, such as PhD programmes, public engagement, and relationships with surrounding ecosystems. The ENLIGHT alliance itself was built upon existing educational contacts and linkages which did not necessarily exist at the research and innovation level. Incorporating R&I into the alliance through SwafS thus meant that the partners and R&I departments had to get to know each other. Initially, this posed a significant obstacle to starting the in-depth work, and while significant strides have been made in this regard over the past three years, the process of mutual understanding is actually still ongoing.

Consequently, setting a joint research agenda among European universities as part of an alliance (which at its core had not been established around R&I) is a long-term and ambitious goal. However, the three-year timeline of the funding provided was, and is still, considered a significant limitation for accomplishing the objectives laid out in the project. In terms of the timeframe of tasks laid out within the three-year lifespan of RISE, a significant portion of the initial phase of the project was dedicated to mapping exercises and constructing the framework for activities. Consequently, the results and outcomes of the project have only begun to become apparent in the most recent months while the project is in its last stages before closing.

Additionally, while the primary focus of the RISE project was on providing support for research rather than conducting research itself, one goal towards the end of the project was to prioritize research activities. However, establishing sustainable scientific collaborations within the ENLIGHT alliance requires a significant investment of time. Each partner university must understand that this initiative is not just a project, but a means to collectively develop and promote transformations. Building trust between research communities within the alliance is thus a crucial component to such a project, as trust is essential for maintaining long-term scientific cooperation. This was made difficult given the short timeline of the RISE project. Additionally, the pandemic disrupted the ability for the research management community to meet in person during the early stages of the project, slowing the process of building these crucial networks.

In addition to challenges based around time, the first Policy Brief also cited a lack of information about future funding as a barrier. However, the RISE project observes today that the real hindrance to developing a long-term research and innovation vision is due in fact to the inadequacy of that funding. As it currently stands, there is no future financing from the alliance available to the

RISE endeavours after the project's closing. Furthermore, subsequent projects within the ENLIGHT alliance cannot guarantee that contact between existing RISE networks can and will be maintained. This can be seen at the operational level through the ENLIGHT Expert Networks focused on R&I which have developed from RISE. These networks formed from the collaboration of partners across the alliance in several different fields of expertise related to the work packages of RISE, including R&I Support, Digital Infrastructures, Research(er) Assessment, Innovation, Public Engagement, Open Science, and Research Impact. As the participants in these networks saw the usefulness of these groups, their goal is to continue to maintain and grow the networks of expertise developed over the course of RISE as alliance-based groups of experts and communities of practice in various fields of R&I/R&I support. However, with no alliance-based funding secured, and only institutional financial support available on a "case by case" basis, this means that the collaboration and cooperation that the RISE project worked so hard to create among its R&I partners runs the risk of weakening in intensity over time, if not disappearing entirely, due to this lack of support. This, unfortunately, would only widen the R&I and educational cooperation gap further in the ENLIGHT alliance.

The RISE project is thus faced with the challenges of sustaining long-term collaboration between its partners with funding which is, ultimately, insufficient for supporting this objective. Lack of funding can have impact both for researchers, in preventing the development of optimal digital solutions for the alliance, as well for R&I support, by resulting in a lack of resources and dedicated support staff at each partner university. Additional staff involvement is necessary for certain tasks, but with heavy workloads already in place, it becomes challenging and detracts from the sense of community across the alliance, (whereby interaction between partners can become more perfunctory than collaborative).

What can be concluded thus is that the limited European funding, lack of extra financial support from some Member States, and budgetary constraints faced by the individual universities has continued, and ultimately will continue, to limit the ability to fully realize an ambitious research and innovation vision for the alliance.

Another difficulty faced by the ENLIGHT alliance over the course of the RISE project has included cultural challenges which impacted communication, cooperation and engagement. This was due to a variety of factors, but included differences in internal organization, research culture, and levels of commitment among the nine partners¹, as originally cited in the first Policy Brief.

One such challenge which has remained relevant during the entire lifespan of the RISE project includes the language and communication barriers. While multilingualism is of the utmost importance to a European alliance, English is the primary means of communication for ENLIGHT and its related projects. However, the RISE project includes 9 different countries and several different languages. While levels of English proficiency (written and/or oral) may vary across the university partners, the most apparent and resilient communication difficulty remains developing a shared and mutually understood lexicon of frequent terms used in the fields of R&I. One specific challenge described in the first policy brief, which is still observable today, includes the varying interpretations and policies surrounding R&I terminology. For example, this can be as simple as semantic discrepancies in individual terms: "academic" (noun) may be synonymous with "researcher" in one university in the alliance, though not at all in another. Likewise, disparities in the use of "PhD candidate" instead of "PhD student" (or even "doctoral candidate" or "doctoral student") can cause confusion or, at the very least, a lack of homogeneity in both written and oral forms of communication. In certain R&I support fields, different partner universities have vastly different terminology for incorporating certain approaches into their official institutional policies. This is certainly the case for research impact, where defining and implementing actions for research impact can vary from university to university. This creates difficulty when trying to identify underlying themes and strategies across the different institutions of the alliance. As a result, these disparities in approaches and definitions, while seemingly minor, can create administrative obstacles which lead to misunderstandings and ultimately slow down progress.

¹ While the ENLIGHT alliance currently includes 10 partners, the University of Bern was not part of the alliance at the onset of the RISE project and thus is understood here to not be an official partner of RISE.

Other barriers related to cultural and operational differences across institutional cultures include differences in resources and commitment. Given the diverse institutional landscapes within the alliance, partner involvement exhibits heterogeneity, sometimes due to a lack of defined strategy or action plan, leadership, or even acknowledgment/recognition within the respective institution. Consequently, this disparity may result in fluctuating levels of commitment and engagement in tasks, alongside knowledge gaps across fields of expertise.

As such, it was identified early on in the RISE project that there was a need to bridge knowledge gaps within partner universities. This could be seen in areas such as Open Science (in particular, public engagement, research data management and FAIR data), rewards and recognition, and to stay informed and aligned on ENLIGHT topics and practices at various levels. This knowledge gap did eventually decrease over the course of the project and significant progress has been made since the early onset of the RISE project.

For RISE, the challenges surrounding timeframe, funding, and communication have continued to remain relevant, with some difficulties becoming more apparent, though unfortunately no long-term solutions have been adopted. The most daunting obstacle for RISE remains sustaining R&I initiatives within the ENLIGHT alliance after the closing of the RISE project. While certain R&I aspects will be carried forward as a part of the alliance's newest project ENLIGHT 2.0, limitations imposed by the Erasmus program may limit the development of the research and innovation dimension. The absence of a subsequent R&I project within the ENLIGHT alliance at the end of RISE, one with clearly defined actions and outcomes, suggests that the collaboration commenced under the RISE project can only be sustained post-project through ad hoc efforts initiated by individual staff members seeking to enhance and preserve research collaboration amongst ENLIGHT partners. However, without a concrete strategy and support in place, achieving long-term success in this endeavour will be challenging. Consequently, the alliance now is at risk of disparate parallel evolution between internal cooperation in the field of education (supported by the Erasmus+ project) and internal cooperation in the field of research and research support (with lacks any allocated funding). Given that university education is grounded in scientific research, this poses a substantial threat to the continued development of a cohesive, high-quality educational portfolio within the ENLIGHT alliance.

2. Please describe how you tackled or intend to **tackle these challenges**. Based on your project's experience so far (and if applicable), briefly outline case(s) that you consider as **good practice** and of interest to other universities or to policy-makers.

and

3. Please describe the **tangible progress** that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project. Please elaborate on whether the inclusive and integrated cooperation approach of your alliance helps accelerate institutional change of all partners (e.g. through sharing of practices from institutions with strong expertise or infrastructure in specific areas to institutions without).

Good practices and tangible progress that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project

The ENLIGHT RISE project has continued to implement different strategies to address the challenges and obstacles outlined in question #1. This has led to real progress and innovation within the project which benefits the alliance as a whole. In the previous version of this Policy Brief, it was noted that, within the first year, the project focused on understanding and familiarizing itself with the research culture, priorities, and profiles of each partner university in the alliance. After a period of 18 months, this knowledge formed the basis for cooperation and laid the groundwork for important

institutional changes. Mapping exercises were conducted to identify potential synergies in research and innovation, and an R&I Observatory and an Impact Repository were created to centralize scientific expertise and best practices.

These developments have had positive, lasting impact across the alliance. For example, inspired by the development of the R&I Observatory in RISE, the University of Tartu has created an accessible dashboard with detailed information about its research groups. Another strong example is the field of research impact, where a variety of measures have been implemented to enhance awareness, literacy, and readiness in relation to impact. These measures include the establishment of the Impact Repository and its online training resources section, the provision of Research Impact training for Research Support Officers (RSO's), the implementation of Impact Awards and appointment of Impact Ambassadors, as well as the organization of several on-site Impact conferences and events. Additionally, the leadership of the FOREU2 impact thematic group, collaboration with the EARMA Impact group, and active participation in numerous conferences and events further contribute to these impact-related initiatives. The impact experts of ENLIGHT will continue in these efforts to promote a culture of impact across the alliance after the RISE project within the context of the ENLIGHT 2.0 project.

Furthermore, workshops, webinars, trainings, and networking events were organized and contributed to mutual learning on various topics of interest, such as research support, open science, public engagement, and impact assessment. Several toolkits were published, including a self-assessment tool on research impact as well as support kits for researchers (e.g. on creating collaborative research proposals), and on Open Science. Additionally in the field of Open Science, joint Open Science principles were developed and endorsed by the ENLIGHT Rectors in order to establish a common basis for an Open Science culture and to express the commitment to implement an 'open by default' approach in teaching, research, outreach and engagement activities, for the benefit of science and society. The adoption of the ENLIGHT Open Science principles has been an important step for universities such as the University of Tartu, as both UT and Estonia as a whole had previously lacked established guidelines for Open Science.

The RISE project also emphasized creating a community within the alliance and increasing mobility through regular meetings, transdisciplinary focus groups, and networks of ambassadors. Seed money and budgets were provided to support collaboration and mobility, and events such as AIMDay, the ENLIGHT Matchmaking Event, and various events around research impact, such as the Impact Conference in 2023 and the Impact Event organized in June 2024. Several joint proposals have also been submitted by the ENLIGHT researchers thanks to the functioning of the focus groups, R&I support group and the use of the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory. Joint governance and staff meetings were held with the E+ community, and regular meetings within each university ensured engagement and involvement. Communication efforts included updating the website, publishing deliverables and documents in open access, and offering language courses and internal training. There was even the creation of the FOREU2 SwafS and Impact thematic subgroups (led by ENLIGHT), which provided a platform to address common challenges and propose innovative solutions between European University Alliances.

At the conclusion of the ENLIGHT RISE project, there is now the question as to how best maintain the tools, initiatives and networks that have been established, as well as the future planning of webinars, training sessions, and networking events. Within the ENLIGHT alliance, the sustainability of these resources remains an important topic of discussion. While it is not yet certain how some of the RISE tools and initiatives will be integrated into the development of the ENLIGHT alliance moving forward, such as the R&I Observatory, pathways are being explored to offer the most relevant and up-to-date solutions for researcher matchmaking for the alliance. Other tools and initiatives have clearer plans for sustainability in the future. One such example is the Impact Repository, which will be in principle maintained after ENLIGHT RISE by UPV/EHU as part of its commitment to the ENLIGHT alliance. Another such example includes the ENLIGHT Expert Networks, an initiative which arose from the communities of experts which formed from and around the RISE work packages. Each of these networks will formulate a commitment on what is considered feasible to continue and support on an in-kind basis in order to continue to share knowledge and best

practices within the alliance. Furthermore, the operational guidelines for these ENLIGHT Expert Networks will serve as the framework for other non-R&I networks formed within the alliance in the future, creating more synergy between the R&I and educational initiatives of ENLIGHT.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (MAX 3P)

In this section, the European Universities pilot Alliances make recommendations in relation to the policy topics identified below. Given the unique strengths and focus of each European University Alliances, please focus only on those aspects of most relevance to your case. Please feel free as well to expand to other policy topics you may wish to share your learnings and recommendations (other recommendations).

1. Policy topic 1: facilitating transnational cooperation

- Knowing that the Commission proposed a Council recommendation to facilitate transnational collaboration between universities, which action should be prioritised to address the challenges you encountered as an Alliance in sharing capacities, infrastructures, resources or staff in R&I?

It was argued in the previous Policy Brief that long-term funding is crucial for the success of alliances in education, research, innovation, and societal transfer, according to a statement from 41 European University Alliances in March 2022. While the inclusion of research and innovation in the new E+ proposal was agreed upon, the lack of dedicated funding for alliance's research and innovation hampers true and sustainable transformation in this area. It is suggested that dedicated funding should support bottom-up collaborations and joint research projects, focusing on curiosity-driven research topics of mutual interest to the alliance.

In order to enhance transnational cooperation in research and innovation, experienced researchers, PhD candidates and early career researchers play a vital role. Lower barriers to the recognition of their skills and training, as well as incentives to expand networks beyond the MSCA scheme, are still deemed necessary to attract skilled researchers. Additionally, there should be improvements in rights retention and exceptions for research, as well as harmonization of legal frameworks regarding open licensing of publications, data, and code. Lastly, Recommendation 10 calls for higher education institutions to involve learners, academics, and researchers more in the governance of transnational cooperation structures.

Regarding the recommendation for collaboration, the sentiment remains unchanged, or possibly slightly amplified. Due to the lack of additional funding available for research support, there is a possibility that this aspect of collaboration may be diminished. A three-year project timeframe may not be sufficient to initiate and sustain a collaborative effort immediately. Furthermore, the RISE collaboration was primarily focused on supporting research staff, whereas researchers have access to funding opportunities from sources (such as Horizon, for example). It is thus crucial to emphasize the importance of engaging R&I support staff in fostering collaboration among partners, as they play a vital, (albeit sometimes overlooked) role in connecting researchers from the ENLIGHT consortium. In light of recent geopolitical developments across Europe, promoting collaboration within these alliances could prove crucial in discussions surrounding internationalization within universities.

2. Policy topic 2: strengthening careers

- Is there a need to develop a model tenure-track system at European level to contribute to solving precariousness of early career researchers? If you believe so, how do you think it should be structured?

The previous Policy Brief took the position that a tenure track system, if well-designed and monitored, could be a solution for career instability in early career researchers and offer clearer career prospects on a global scale. However, it should be noted that creating a model that respects universities' autonomy in recruiting academic staff and addresses differences in academic and legal systems would be challenging. Implementing a suitable tenure track system would bring clarity and value to academic careers, prompting European universities and research institutions to reconsider their current approaches. Standardizing the roles of Assistant, Associate, and full Professor, as well as standardizing the requirements and procedures for accessing these positions, across the European Union would be highly beneficial, requiring a set of competencies that are not overly restrictive and incorporate input from research assessment working groups. This would promote mobility and accommodate individuals at different stages of their careers. The system could eventually encompass not only research positions but also essential roles in managing research workflows, research outputs, teaching, and learning.

Today, the position taken surrounding career instability and precariousness for Early Career Researchers in the first policy brief remains relevant. Early Career Researchers remain an important part of the European agenda, as the European Commission has introduced a set of measures to improve the European Research Area and make it more resilient, appealing, and competitive. This is in line with their goal of promoting attractive and sustainable research careers. As such, the outlook remains positive for the ECR objectives within the alliance to be supported on a European level.

- In light of the policy process on the reform of assessment of research and institutions, what are your recommendations on how to address academic/researcher career assessment?

It was highlighted within the first Policy Brief that the partner universities in ENLIGHT RISE recognized the need for research assessment system reform and support the process led by the 'coalition of the willing'. A Research Assessment Working Group in ENLIGHT RISE is following the European initiative (Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment - CoARA) and comparing assessment systems across the alliance. As of now, several, (if not most, according to a report conducted by the Researcher Assessment Working Group of RISE), universities have already begun reforming and innovating their assessment practices and have joined CoARA. While the partner universities are all moving towards the same goal, they are at different stages in the reform process. This disparity in the advancement of university reforms can be attributed to both internal university issues and external factors, which include national evaluation schemes and legislation. ENLIGHT RISE sees the advantages in the direction set by CoARA but also respects the autonomy of universities to design and implement their own reform process.

It was previously argued that academic/researcher career assessments should reward diverse achievements in research outputs and activities, such as publications, data, code, research design, mentoring, teaching, software development, innovation, peer review, and engagement with stakeholders. It should also recognize efforts for impact, Open Science, gender equality, equal opportunities, and inclusiveness. This observation is considered still relevant today as the RISE project comes to a close, as engaging academic staff at all levels remains crucial for designing and implementing inclusive research assessments.

3. Policy topic 3: digital transition

- What are the specific needs of the alliances to accelerate their digital transition in the R&I dimension, and how can this be addressed at the EU level?
- In particular, do you see a need for *additional* dedicated e-infrastructures for data storage and management that are distributed and interoperable? Please take into account progress regarding the development of the federated e-infrastructure for research outputs (EOSC, see [ERA Policy Agenda](#)), and the implementation of a digital platform for cooperation in higher education (see the [European strategy for universities](#)).

Originally, the first Policy Brief pointed out the need for resources in order to create joint digital systems in R&I. ENLIGHT RISE, at that time, was developing a digital matching tool for funding and researcher collaboration but lacked significant resources to do so. To address this, the researchers were interested in establishing a joint researcher database within their alliance. However, it was important to avoid each alliance creating their own e-infrastructures, as this would be costly and hinder knowledge exchange. It was put forth that the EU could play a role in defining the framework for such e-infrastructures to reduce variability. Another consideration to take into account was notably GDPR and sensitive data. Cooperation between higher education institutions requires agreement on the interpretation of GDPR's definition of personal data, as well as requirements for handling sensitive data. Security measures such as encryption and two-factor authentication would be necessary for handling sensitive data. The use of federated data analyses with DataShield is also an option. The definition and implementation of a "federated e-infrastructure" within EOSC is still being explored. Several ENLIGHT partners contribute to the development of the EOSC, in particular, through disciplinary research infrastructures (national and international, as described in the WP3 reports).

Moving forward, the digital matching tool was not developed in the course of the RISE project. Apart from issues related to costs, the compatibility of systems and data protection remain a crucial question, with issues involving privacy and sensitive data. A highly successfully matchmaking event was organized in its place. This event used the support of the b2match platform, which is an online event networking platform used for organizing online meetings, messaging between registered participants as well as posting collaboration requests, proposals, and opportunities. This platform is a useful, affordable resource, though for all of its benefits, it does have some noteworthy limitations. Researchers have to create a profile in order to have access to the aforementioned functionalities. This alleviates the issue of data protection as identified for the matchmaking tool. However, as these researcher profiles are voluntarily created, this means that profiles may vary in terms of detail and "up-to-date-ness" over the course of the lifespan of the platform. Researchers must take the initiative to not only create a profile but update it regularly in order to fully benefit from the matchmaking service. This is an issue also associated with the R&I observatory, which, while a significant tool developed under the umbrella of the RISE project, must be manually updated and may thus be limited in the detail it can offer for connecting researchers across the universities of ENLIGHT.

4. Policy topic 4: access to excellence

- What is your advice on how to accelerate access to excellence in science and in value creation for all participants for higher education institutions across the entire ERA, through the European Universities Initiative?

During the first Policy Brief, the advice on accelerating access to excellence in science included focusing the alliance's efforts on transparency, research quality, and responsible open science, while also addressing resource allocation, recognition, and networking. As it was initially pointed out, calls

which encourage cross-alliance cooperation could provide opportunities to significantly enhance excellence and promote career growth (this was identified as including activities such as “piloting of collaborations, mentoring and training, setting up an integrated research information system which brings together internal information dealing with research output, ongoing research projects, new research ideas, HR-related information on research-performing staff, research infrastructure, etc.”). However, scientific excellence shouldn't be limited to only impact-driven research; it should also include fundamental and curiosity-driven research.

Moving into the future, it is important to take into consideration new documents and reports which highlight value creation in higher education institutions, such as the “Council recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation, and entrepreneurial talents in Europe”, (released in December 2023). This report aims to retain European researchers and improve the EU's appeal as a destination for international talents. Its contents include a comprehensive definition of a researcher as well as a layout of ways to enhance the attractiveness of research careers. Reports such as this, which address concerns about undervaluing researchers by acknowledging the roles of research and project managers and outlining their shared goals, are thus valuable for establishing an alliance-oriented approach for fostering value creation and accelerating access to excellence in science.

When defining excellence, the alliance should consider qualitative, cultural, and social aspects, ensuring equal opportunities for individuals regardless of their demographics. ENLIGHT RISE highlights initiatives like regional academies and collaboration with external partners to promote research initiatives. According to the European Commission, strong knowledge creation and innovation hubs rely on a community of Research and Innovation (R&I) managers. Research support is thus crucial for scientific excellence but is often undervalued and associated with uncertain career paths. The EU should encourage member states and universities to invest in research support staff, skills development, and better career prospects.

5. Policy topic 5: increasing global competitiveness

- Europe's relative weight at a global level when it comes to research-intensive universities is shrinking. In light of this, a European Excellence Initiative will be established to improve global competitiveness of Europe's universities, in synergy with the European Universities Initiative of Erasmus+. In your view, what would be key elements of such an Initiative? Secondly, could you envisage that such an initiative specifically targets EU objectives such as the Green Deal or European Missions?

ENLIGHT RISE acknowledged, in the previous Policy Brief, its support for the European Excellence initiative. However, it was and remains important to highlight the potential limitations of the WIDERA work programme, particularly in terms of consortium composition and ambitions. It was suggested that global collaborations and targeted collaborations for skills development, training, and sharing of infrastructures and expertise be considered. While recognizing the importance of the EU objectives, we emphasized the need for a broad and strong European research base, cautioning against overly selective investments in specific research fields.

Now, with the end of the RISE project in sight, a possible future for the ENLIGHT alliance would broaden its scope beyond Europe and engage in collaboration from a more global perspective. While within this approach there may not be access to Erasmus funding, such cooperation could involve other universities and enhance overall collaboration efforts for both education and potential R&I initiatives. Although this is part of the ENLIGHT 2.0 initiative as the current project of the ENLIGHT alliance, future R&I projects should pay attention to and take note of the exact measures that will be implemented in this regard.

6. Other recommendations

In the previous Policy Brief, it was put forward that advocacy is essential to secure long-term financial support for alliances from Member States. This observation remains true today, as these alliances aim to permanently transform partner institutions by collectively conducting training, education, and research. To gain credibility and support, these transformative projects require significant funding in the initial years to facilitate staff, student, and academic mobility, as well as joint projects. The alliances will thus need to adopt new methods and visions in order to develop robust and fruitful collaborations. Successful results could potentially encourage national funding agencies in European countries to increasingly contribute to sustainable support. Likewise, establishing a sustainable and long-term funding mechanism at the EU level will further facilitate national support. As it has been elaborated above in this updated Policy Brief while identifying challenges and barriers, sustaining project objectives and collaborations beyond the scope of the project lifespan requires concrete support of both allocated time and funding. This must come from the institutional, national, and European levels. Without these, the cooperation, results, and communities, painstakingly built within European alliance initiatives run the risk of disappearing.

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